

TOPOLOGY AWARE LOAD BALANCING FOR GRIDS

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ABSTRACT

Load balancing functionalities are crucial for best Grid performance and utilization. Accordingly, this paper presents a new meta-scheduling method called TunSys. It is inspired from the natural phenomenon of heat propagation and thermal equilibrium. TunSys is based on a Grid polyhedron model with a spherical like structure used to ensure load balancing through a local neighborhood propagation strategy. Furthermore, experimental results compared to FCFS, DGA and HGA show encouraging results in terms of system performance and scalability and in terms of load balancing efficiency.

KEYWORDS

Grid computing, meta-scheduling, distributed load balancing, topology-aware.

1. INTRODUCTION

Grid computing[1] extends existing distributed computing to a more unified and collaborative structure. It enables multiple computing resources, that are geographically distributed and owned by different individuals or organizations, to be logically coupled to form the illusion of a powerful super computer with infinite capacity[2]. Scheduling and load balancing are essential grid software infrastructure services. These services assign tasks to nodes (*i.e.* computing resources) and transfer tasks from overloaded to under-loaded nodes in order to maximize resource utilization on one hand, and minimizing the total task's execution time on the other hand. Considering the grid load balancing problem, several solutions have been proposed using different methods and strategies, *e.g.*, [3][4].

Sofar, proposed methods can be classified into various categories depending on the point of interest: centralized vs. decentralized, decision taking [5 – 8], local vs. global optimization approach [9][10], static vs. dynamic strategies [11][3], adaptive vs. non-adaptive behavior [12][13], etc.

Among the most critical issues pertaining to grids is how to manage the resources [4]. In the proposed solution, the grid resources are organized according to a logical topology called the resource management model [4]. This topology/model defines how the different grid entities communicate and work in order to achieve the received jobs/tasks. R. Buyya et al. proclaimed that the choice of the right model for the resource management architecture plays a major role in its eventual (commercial) success [4].

The motivation behind this paper is based on the observation that the load balancing problem can be improved by simply improving the classical used models tree, star, and P2P and further proposing a new one; a polyhedron sphere like model that was introduced for the first time in [14]. This logical model has the merit of providing optimized load balancing in a stateless context. It guarantees a high level of decentralization and scalability of the load balancing process leading to better resource utilization rates and minimum tasks execution time. Therefore, this work proposes a decentralized topology-aware load balancing solution for independent tasks in a grid environment

named TunSys. The grid topology is constructed automatically in two steps. In the first step, a polyhedron topology, that has a sphere-like structure, is created. In the second step, the available resources are assigned to the nodes of the logical topology depending on the resource's physical characteristics. This structure is used to ensure a local neighborhood load balancing strategy. The presented method is dynamic, adaptive, cooperative, and non-preemptive. In addition, it uses a combination of two load thresholds: local and global. The experimental evaluation of the proposed model using the GridSim simulator has shown encouraging results in terms of makespan, system's scalability which can reach linear and supra-linear levels, and load balancing performance outperforming FCFS (*First-come-first-served Algorithm*) [5], DGA (*Dynamic Genetic load balancing Algorithm*) [7], and in most cases HGA (*A hybrid load balancing strategy of sequential tasks for grid computing environments*) [6].

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 gives a brief overview of the related work. Section 3 describes the proposed logical polyhedron topology. Section 4 presents the proposed adaptive load balancing method. Section 5 discusses the simulation results. Finally, the paper's conclusion highlights some future research directions.

1.1 RELATED WORK

The Grid load balancing problem have been widely studied. Indeed, the literature contains several solutions using different strategies to solve the problem from different points of view. They can be classified according to different criteria: centralized vs. decentralized, local vs. global, static vs. dynamic, adaptive vs. non-adaptive, threshold-based vs. threshold-independent, etc. Further details of the largely adopted taxonomy is well explained by Yagoubi et al. In [15], an excellent survey on Grid resource allocation mechanisms is presented in [24, 25]. As examined in these detailed works, some of the proposed methods use agents [5], [11], [14], [26 – 29] to take profit from their decentralized, autonomous, and interacting character and thus avoid the "single point of failure". Some methods use genetic algorithms [5 – 7], [30] as a means to approximate solutions in polynomial complexity of the problem that can "evolve" during the operation of the parallel computing system.

Actually, this work focuses on two major characteristics: (i) the centralization vs. decentralization of the scheduling and load balancing processes, and (ii) their awareness of the network topology.

1.1.1 Centralized vs. decentralized load balancing methods

Many authors tried to find out whether it is better to decentralize or to centralize the load balancing process to fit the decentralized nature of the grid resources or to have a strong control on the tasks allocation decision.

In [6], Yajun Li and al. proposed a centralized load balancing scheme for sequential tasks. In [7] many issues are considered such as threshold policies, information exchange criteria, and inter-processor communication for a centralized solution. Li gang and al. [23] proposed two load balancing techniques according to the QoS requirement. The mean arrival rate is utilized by the central node to calculate the mean number of jobs in the waiting queues.

Liang Bai and al. [8] proposed to organize the grid nodes into multiple ant colonies. At the beginning, ants are distributed on computing nodes randomly. The ants move through computing nodes and assign the tasks based on pheromone and heuristic information until all tasks have been allocated. The load balancing approach is decentralized and collaborative. Another ant-like self-organizing mechanism is applied using agents by Junwei Cao [18], to perform complementary load balancing for batch jobs with no explicit execution deadlines. However, the main problem of these

two solutions is the high number of exchanged messages implying high network resource consumption by the load balancing process.

Junwei Cao and al. work [5] used a combination of both intelligent agents and multi-agent approaches. Agents are organized into a tree: the broker heads the whole hierarchy and the coordinators head a sub-hierarchy. Each agent is a representative of a local grid resource and utilizes predictive application performance data and iterative heuristic algorithms to ensure local load balancing across multiple hosts.

1.1.2 Topology aware vs. unaware load balancing methods

The grid resources are physically interconnected to each other using network devices and cables forming a physical topology. While the system and workload model designate how the different parts of the system are logically organized and what kind of tasks it is supposed to achieve [4]. These models are key factors of the grid load balancing problem

In fact, the Grid must scale from few nodes up to a huge number of nodes. In addition, the system has to deal with the problems of node failure or unavailability and unexpected peaks of load, and it must be able to take all necessary corrective decisions. Furthermore, the part of resources consumed by the Grid load management process must be kept to an absolute minimum so as to maximize the resource utilization efficiency. Finally, the computing power consumed by a scheduler may be considered as a criterion of the scheduler selection [10]. The high amounts of computing and storage resources used by the decision making process would be considered as serious drawback like in [6].

Figure .1 Tree (a), Star (b), and P2P system and workload model

The word Grid *topology* can describe the physical and/or logical arrangement of the nodes. It is often used to mean the logical topology, especially for open Grids where the Grid developers cannot predict the physical topology [2 – 4].

Many topology-aware scheduling and load balancing algorithms have been proposed which use different Grid topologies. They implement simple models like Tree [14 – 17], Peer-to-Peer [18 – 20], mesh [30], star [22, 23], etc. Even though these models are the most popular in the literature, real grid model scan integrate different sub-topologies at different levels.

Three cases are possible while constructing the Grid logical topology: It can be totally independent, partially dependent, or identical to the physical one. Camille Coti et al. [33] discussed how to organize communication patterns within applications with respect to the underlying physical topology. Because the various communication patterns induce different performances, the authors assume that an application ends up communicating back and forth between clusters if the inappropriate physical topology is used; such communication significantly impacts the performances. And in [34], the authors suggested a service for the delivery of dynamic

performance information in Grid environments. They suggested that reflecting the real network topology in the application might improve the interface data structure.

This work proposes a new decentralized solution based on an innovative system model (referred to using the word "topology") in order to put in evidence the importance of the network. In fact, "the network is the computer" [35]. The proposed topology is decentralized, scalable, and well adapted to the grid load balancing process like in tree topology but doesn't "need the assistance of its direct parent" [24]. The nodes are interconnected to each other to form a sphere-like polyhedron constructed in two steps. Unlike the star topology, it does not need a central point to coordinate the load balancing process. It is "resilient to network traffic to deliver optimal performance" keeping the amount of network and computing resources needed for grid management in an absolute minimum since "the computing power consumed by a scheduler may be considered as a criterion of the scheduler selection"[36]. The next section presents the proposed topology: the structure construction, the resources assignment heuristic, and the local search algorithm used for topology optimization.

1.2 THE POLYHODRON GRID TOPOLOGY

The Grid topology refers to the layout of connected nodes. It is the highest level defining how the nodes are physically and logically interconnected. The physical topology means the physical design of the Grid including the devices, location and network cable installation. The logical topology, on the other hand, refers to the way the different nodes and clusters constituting the Grid cooperate to execute the tasks.

The proposed polyhedron topology was inspired from the natural phenomenon of heat propagation in nature. In fact, heat spreads from a hot body to a cold body. This is called heat exchange process (or thermal equilibrium). The objects with sphere shape are a well-adapted form to heat spreading [37][38]. Heat spreads from the point of contact in a balanced manner until the total coverage of the spherical surface or total absorption. Similarly, during the proposed load balancing process, tasks are balanced from the overloaded nodes to the under loaded ones until equilibrium or task execution.

The proposed polyhedron topology is constructed in two steps: the polyhedron structure is created, then the grid nodes are assigned to the logical positions.

1.2 Creation of the Grid polyhedron topology structure

The proposed topology of the Grid has a polyhedron structure with a sphere-like form (0a)[39]. This structure facilitates the adoption of a local load balancing strategy.

Figure .2 Grid Topology (a) Grid nodes organized as a polyhedron (b) Example of load situation

The construction of this structure is performed in two steps: First, connecting the nodes to form a flat 2D Grid like structure, then adding connections to obtain the final spherical like form. The flat 2D grid structure must be the nearest possible to a squared one.

To clarify this Grid topology, let us start by describing the first “flat view” of the Grid. A 2D Grid composed of p lines and m columns where $m = \left\lfloor \frac{n}{\lfloor \sqrt{n} \rfloor} \right\rfloor$ and $p = \lfloor \sqrt{n} \rfloor$ with $n = |X|$ is constructed. The

values of m and p are fixed so that the $m \times p$ grid is the nearest possible to a squared one. If $m = p$ then n is a square and a squared grid is obtained. If $n = m \times p$ and $m \neq p$ then a grid of size $p \times m$ is obtained. Otherwise, a partial $(p+1)^{\text{th}}$ line that contains only $k = n - (m \times p)$ nodes is added to the grid of p lines and m columns. 0 shows an example of the resulting 2D Grid for $n=10$ (0a), $n=25$ (0b). After node’s connection, the polyhedron form of the Grid will have a spherical-like structure.

Figure .3 Example of the 2D view of the Grid: (a) $n=10$ (b) $n=25$

Afterward, each internal node is connected to its four neighbors (instructions [4-7]). As a result, external nodes are connected to only three neighbors, whereas the Grid corners are connected only to two neighbors. Then external nodes at the top (respectively, at the right) are connected to nodes at the bottom (respectively, at the left) of the Grid (instructions [8 - 10]). The corner nodes at the extreme right of the two last lines are connected. Connections between the Grid nodes (graphically represented in 0[39]) are resumed as follows:

- Instructions [4 , 7]: Each node at position (i,j) in the flat view where $1 < i < p$ and $1 < j < m$ is connected to the nodes at positions $(i-1,j)$, $(i+1,j)$, $(i,j-1)$ and $(i,j+1)$.
- If $n = m \times p$ then:
 - each node at position $(1,j)$ is connected to the node (p,j)
 - each node at position $(i,1)$ is connected to the node (i,m)
- If $n > m \times p$ then (instructions[5, 6, 9, 10]):
 - each node $(1,j)$ where $1 \leq j \leq k$ is connected to the node $(p+1,j)$.
 - each node $(1,j)$ where $k < j \leq m$ is connected to the node (p,j) .
 - the node $(p+1,k)$ is connected to the node (p,m)

- the node (p+1,k) is connected to the node (p+1,1)
- each node (i,1) where $1 \leq i \leq p$ is connected to the node (i,m).

The construction of the Grid structure is handled in a time $O(n)$ for a Grid with n nodes. In the worst case, the Grid has a total number of connections equal to:

$$|R| = \begin{cases} 2 \times p \times m & \text{if } (n = p \times m) \\ n + m \times p + 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The algorithm complexity is equal to: $\Theta(n) = 2 \times n + 4$

1.2.1 Resource assignment to the polyhedron topology

It is beneficial to construct a logical topology that takes into account the characteristics of the physical one [34]. For example, when the network data transmission speed is high between two nodes, tasks are going to take less time to move from node to another. Thus the load balancing process will be improved if these nodes are neighbors (interconnected) in the logical topology.

The assignment of the resources to the nodes of the polyhedron logical topology depends on the physical network characteristics. In this context, the proposed topology reflects partially the physical one since its construction is based on an abstraction view of the physical network. To maximize the efficiency of the logical topology, resources having a high connection quality must be neighbors in the polyhedron topology.

To do so, a weight G_{ik} that measures the connection quality between the resource r_i and the resource r_k is assigned to each pair of resources (r_i, r_k) . The weight G_{ik} reflects different network parameters: baud rate, maximum transmission unit (MTU), and propagation delay. In [3] and [11], since the proposed solution is centralized, the authors quantified the connection quality of each node by dividing its transmission rate by the network bandwidth of the dispatcher. In [40] the network performance between two sites is calculated using two parameters: transmission delay representing the start-up cost and contention delays at intermediate links and a data transmission rate representing the available bandwidth.

The assignment of the nodes to the constructed logical topology depends on the weight between resources: if two resources have a high weight, then they are more susceptible to be assigned to connected nodes according to the logical topology and vice versa.

In the logical topology, each node x_i is logically interconnected to $V(x_i)$ nodes then the weight between the resources assigned to the node x_i and each node in $V(x_i)$ has to be maximized. For a given node $x_i \in X$ the quantity z_i , which is the profit the node x_i brings to the global grid topology, is computed as follows:

$$Z_i = \prod_{x_j \in V(x_i)} \omega_{\pi_i \pi_j}$$

Where $G_{\pi_i \pi_j}$ is the weight between the resource Π_i assigned to the node x_i and the resource Π_j assigned to its neighbor x_j . A higher z_i means a better network exchanging quality in the neighborhood of the node x_i . In 0b, the node x_{18} neighbor's set is: $V(x_{18}) = \{x_{15}, x_{17}, x_6, x_{19}\}$. The profit the node x_{18} brings to the whole topology is $Z_{18} = G_{\pi_{18}, \pi_{15}} \times G_{\pi_{18}, \pi_{17}} \times G_{\pi_{18}, \pi_6} \times G_{\pi_{18}, \pi_{19}}$. If the nodes $(x_{18}, x_{15}, x_{17}, x_6, x_{19})$ are assigned to the resources $(r_1, r_5, r_{14}, r_{20}, r_3)$ then $Z_{18} = Z_{1,5} \times Z_{1,17} \times Z_{1,16} \times Z_{1,15}$. In the computation of the network exchanging quality at node x_i , the product of the weight rather than the sum, is used to reduce the compensation between high values and low values of G_i .

Furthermore, the assignment of the resources to the nodes of the logical topology must maximize the profit of the whole Grid which is equal to the sum of the profits of all the nodes. The assignment of the resources to the nodes of the logical topology aims at maximizing the objective function:

$$Z = \sum_{k=1}^n Z_k.$$

A solution to this problem is a permutation $\Pi=(\Pi_1, \Pi_2, \dots, \Pi_n)$ where Π_i is the resource assigned to the logical node x_i . So the number of possible solutions is equal to $n!$.

Note that the resource assignment to the logical nodes of the polyhedron is a combinatorial optimization problem which can be resolved either by an exact method like simplex algorithm, dynamic programming, or by approximate methods. In this case, the goal is a solution that maximizes as best as possible the objective function Z in a polynomial time. The studied problem needs to be solved (only have a good quality solution) in real (short) time and using the absolute minimum of resources. Consequently, it was considered useful to solve it heuristically by the use of a constructive algorithm followed by a local search to improve the obtained solution. In this case, the optimality of the solution cannot be guaranteed. However, the time required to obtain this solution will be much lower and can even be dead-lined (obviously in this case the quality of the solution strongly depends on the time allowed for the algorithm to get it).

1.2.1 The construction heuristic

The construction heuristic starts from an empty solution $\pi = \emptyset$. It selects randomly a resource r and a node x and assigns r to x . Then, iteratively, it selects one occupied node x of the logical topology still having idle neighbors according to the logical topology and assigns to them the most profitable resources according to network quality criterion Z_x . The algorithm ends when all the resources are assigned thus all the logical nodes are occupied.

Let $R=\{r_1, \dots, r_n\}$ and $X=\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ denote respectively the set of resources and nodes. Initially, the set of idle nodes $IX = X$ and the set of free resources $FR = R$. A node x of the logical topology is idle if neither resource is assigned to it. A resource r is free if it is affected to any logical node. A resource r is assigned to exactly one logical node and a logical node receives a sole resource.

The algorithm starts by selecting a random resource r_i from FR ($i \in \langle 1, n \rangle$) and a random node x_j ($j \in \langle 1, n \rangle$). A partial solution $\pi = \{\pi_{ij}\}$ is obtained and the set of idle nodes and free resources are updated ($FR = FR \setminus \{r_i\}$) and ($IX = X \setminus \{x_j\}$). Given a partial solution π , a given node x have three possible states:

- The node x is idle i.e. no resource is affected to the node x .
- The node x is occupied by a resource but at least one of its local neighbors is idle. The node x is, then, still unlocked.
- The node x is locked i.e. the node x and all its neighbors are occupied

The set of unlocked nodes is stored in the list Q . The algorithm affects iteratively resources to unlocked nodes until all nodes are locked. The most profitable unlocked node is selected and the free resources are assigned to its idle neighbors.

Algorithm 1: The construction heuristic

- 1) FR := {x_j ; j ∈ <1, n>}
 - 2) IX := {x_j ; j ∈ <1, n>}
 - 3) r := random (FR)
 - 4) x := random (IX)
 - 5) Π_i := φ
 - 6) Π_i := Π ∪ {Π_{rx}}
 - 7) Q_i := {x}
 - 8) FR := FR \ {x}
 - 9) IX := IX \ {r}
 - 10) While (Q ≠ φ) Do
 - x_j := max Z_k, k ∈ Q
 - update FR
 - update IX
 - update Q
 - update Π
- EndWhile.

The complexity of the construction heuristic is $\Theta(n^2)$.

1.2.2 Local search

After obtaining an initial solution Π_0 with the profit Z_0 , it is improved through local search. During each local search iteration, the algorithm *local search* tries to find all possible permutations between the resources assigned to two distinct nodes x_i and x_j that can lead to a new solution Π_{new} such that $Z_{new} > Z_{old}$. The best generated solution is kept as initial solution at the next iteration. The grid system keeps trying to find good permutations till impossibility of improving the achieved solution. It is possible that the finally obtained solution is not the optimal one. Indeed, the algorithm looks for local minima. It converges rapidly. This keeps the used algorithm in harmony with one of the proposed topology's goal which is to minimize the grid's system load and give resources privilege to the user's jobs. The complexity of each iteration of the local search is $O(n^2)$ since the size of the neighborhood is C_n^2 and the cost of the fitness variation is:

$$O(2 * |V(x)|)$$

A solution of the problem is coded as an assignment vector of size n (n is the number of resources). $\Pi[i]=j$ means that the resource r_j is assigned to node x_i . The neighborhood of the solution $N(\Pi)$ is composed of all assignment vectors obtained after the permutation of two members $\Pi[i]$ and $\Pi[j]$ ($i \neq j$). ($|N(\Pi)| = C_n^2$).

For each generated solution Π , the variation of the cost is computed.

$$\Delta_z = Z(\Pi) - Z(\Pi_0) = (Z_i^{\Pi} + Z_j^{\Pi}) - (Z_i^{\Pi_0} + Z_j^{\Pi_0}) + \sum_{k \in V(i)} (Z_k^{\Pi_0} - Z_k^{\Pi} * \frac{\omega_{kj}}{\omega_{ki}}) + \sum_{k \in V(j)} (Z_k^{\Pi_0} - Z_k^{\Pi} * \frac{\omega_{ki}}{\omega_{kj}})$$

Z_i^{Π} is the local network quality of node i in solution Π if $\Delta_z > 0$. The local search algorithm is given in the following algorithm. As a result, the cost of the generation and the evaluation of the neighborhood is $O(n^2)$.

Algorithm 2: Local search

```

Local:=false
While (local=false) do
    ΔZbest:=0
    For each i,j in <1..n>, i<j do
        ΔZ (Πi←Πj)
        If(ΔZ > ΔZbest)Then
            BestExchange:=Πi←Πj
            ΔZbest :=ΔZ
        EndIF
    End For each
    If(ΔZbest > 0)
        Π0:=Permute(Π0,BestExchange)
        Z:=Z(Π0)+ΔZbest
    Else
        Local:=true
    End if
End while.
Return Π0

```

2. ADAPTIVE LOAD BALANCING

TunSys uses an adaptive and fully decentralized load balancing strategy. The workload is evaluated periodically both globally at the grid level and locally at the node’s level and the load thresholds are adapted. Due to polyhedron logical topology, every node has a set of neighboring nodes. So, the overload propagates from the overloaded nodes to their neighbors and from neighbors to neighbors until a balance of the workload is reached. When the overall grid workload is high, the local and global thresholds are updated so as the nodes can absorb more jobs and the workload balance can be realized overall the grid.

Each node makes local decisions according to its state and the state of its neighbors. In case of unexpected peak of load, the node initiates a sender side load balancing process and the jobs are routed to relatively idle nodes in its local neighborhood. The scheduling process is also based on local decision and is fully decentralized. Each node creates schedules that consider local objectives and constraints within the boundaries of the overall system objectives.

2.1 Global and local load thresholds

Let Q_i , $i \in \langle 1, n \rangle$ be the waiting queue of node I_i and $|Q_i|$ be the length of the tasks waiting to be executed on the node I_i . Let $V(i)$ be the set of neighbors of the node I_i according to the logical topology.

The node's load is evaluated using a load upper bound α_i . If the node’s queue $|Q_i|$ length exceeds α_i it is considered as an overloaded node ($|Q_i| > \alpha_i$). Initially, for a given node x_i , the upper bound is evaluated according to the global Grid load thresholds α and β and the number of its processing elements $|PEs_i|$:

$$\alpha_i = \alpha \times |PEs_i|$$

The thresholds α represents the upper bound of the global Grid load. It represents the load indicator of the waiting queues at the Grid level. Initially, $\alpha=2$; later the system periodically collects

information about the current load and waiting queue length of all the Grid nodes, and it adapts α dynamically according to the resource load variation as follows:

$$\alpha_{\text{new}} = \alpha_{\text{old}} * (1 + \gamma) \quad \text{while } (1 + \gamma) \in]0, 2[\text{ and } \alpha > 1$$

Where γ is an indicator of the current workload state and is computed according to the following formula:

$$\gamma = \frac{\left| \left\{ x_i / \frac{|Q_i|}{PES_i} > M + E \right\} \right|}{|X|} - \frac{\left| \left\{ x_i / \frac{|Q_i|}{PES_i} \leq M - E \right\} \right|}{|X|}$$

Where:

- M is the mean of grid node's load $M = \text{AVG}(|Q_i|, x_i \in X)$
- E is the standard deviation of the grid node's load $E = \text{STD}(|Q_i|, x_i \in X)$

A given node is considered as overloaded if the length of its queue per processing element is more than a standard deviation over the load's mean. A given node is considered as under-loaded if the length of its queue per processing element is less than the loads mean minus the standard deviation of the node's load.

The value of γ is in the interval $]-1, 1[$. A positive value shows that the majority of the nodes are overloaded ($\gamma > 0$) where a negative value shows that there are more under-loaded nodes than overloaded ones ($\gamma < 0$). The combination of the two measures (average and standard deviation) makes the threshold α sensible not only to the grid's peak of load (when the grid load average increases) but also to the spread out of this load.

When the value of γ is positive, local peak of loads are detected and the value of the global threshold is increased and thus the local ones. So, the under-loaded nodes can accept the reception of more jobs and the most overloaded nodes will be discharged in priority.

When the value of γ is negative, the value of the global threshold is decreased and intuitively the local one's. The state of some node's may change from the underload to the overload state and the load propagation process may be inhibited. In fact, if the proportion of under-loaded nodes is high, the load have to be balanced overall the nodes so as to speed up the response time overall the grid.

2.1.1 Load balancing process

The loadbalancing process is triggered or stopped in any node x of the Grid depending on the following scenarios:

- A new task arrives to x_i : When x_i receives a task, its local workload queue is reevaluated. If x_i is already overloaded or if the acceptance of this task will make it overloaded ($|Q_i| > \alpha_i$), then x_i triggers the load balancing process; otherwise the task is inserted into the waiting queue of x_i .
- x_i receives a new value of the global threshold α : x_i updates its local threshold α_i and checks its new load state:
 - If α decreased and if x_i becomes over-loaded ($|Q_i| > \alpha_i$), then x_i triggers the load balancing process in the sender initiated mode.
 - If α increased, then the waiting queue $|Q_i|$ can accept more tasks. Therefore, if the load sender had initiated the balancing process, then it is stopped.

Generally, each load balancing and load sharing algorithm can be defined by three rules: the location rule, the distribution rule and the selection rule [41] :

- The location rule defines which grid resources will be included in the balancing process.
- The distribution rule decides how to redistribute the workload among available nodes.
- The selection rule selects tasks in an overloaded node for reassignment to an under-loaded node.

In the proposed solution, the logical neighborhood relation defined by the polyhedron topology is used to perform the load balancing. This topology has a spherical like structure and a given node x of the grid has $V(x)$ neighbors. The overload is transferred from neighbors to neighbors until complete absorption. The load balancing process is decentralized.

Each node x_i ($i \in \langle 1, n \rangle$) checks its load state based on its current waiting queue and local threshold α_i . Periodically, each node sends information about its load level to its neighbors. In fact, a given node maintains neighborhood's Load table (NL). Such table represents a snapshot of a small part of the grid. Each node perceives its load state and those of its neighbors and decides on the launching of the balancing process based on this local vision of the load spread. This local decision process applies the following rules:

Figure.4 NL table for node x_{11} .

Location rule: In case a node x_i becomes overloaded, it tries to find an under-loaded node x_j from its neighbors $V(x_i)$ ready to receive some jobs. In the example of 0b, node 18 for instance, can send jobs only to nodes 19, 17, 6 and 15.

Distribution rule: The chosen neighbor is the least loaded one. If all elements of $V(x_i)$ are overloaded (x_i and all its neighbors), then x_i does not wait until one of its neighbors becomes under-loaded. It directly sends it to the least loaded one which in turn has to balance it to one of its neighbors.

Selection rule: In this work, an Early and Late [11] technique is applied for the queue management in order to adapt task execution to non-deterministic nature of the Grid computations. At the node level, tasks in its waiting queue $|Q_i|$ are sorted according to their submission time; the oldest tasks are favored for more fairness. In case a task had been delayed for being balanced from node to node, it is fostered while waiting in the queue. In case a task has to be transferred to an under-loaded node, the last one in the queue is selected since it is the last to be submitted to the Grid.

Accordingly, the node's local neighborhood and the equilibration of overload are relayed from neighbors to neighbors—imitating the heat propagation principle. The situation of starvation can

be avoided whenever there is the overload spread from overloaded part of the grid to the under-loaded one.

3. EXPERIMENTATION

The GridSim simulator [42] was used and extended with several classes and interfaces to fulfill specific requirements of TunSys and to take into account the semantics of node description and different resource types. The proposed solution has been simulated in the context of a private Grid context as defined in [17]. The evaluation focuses on the workload balance, the completion time and the scalability. Each experiment has been repeated 10 times. The results are discussed in terms of the mean values.

3.1 The evaluation metrics

The *mean square deviation criteria* is used to evaluate the resource load balancing performance. *It is computed* as follows:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (P_i - \bar{P})^2}{m}}$$

where P_i , \bar{P} denotes the individual node utilization and the average node utilization and m is the number of resources. This metric indicates how well the loads are balanced across all the nodes involved in a grid system. The lower the measurement of this performance metric is, the better the performance of load balancing is. When the value of the *mean square deviation is high, a large gap between the node's workloads is deduced and thus picks of overloads and valleys of underloads may exist.*

To verify if the load balancing process is optimizing the completion time, the *makespan* metric has been used which represents the latest completion time among all the tasks, i.e. the derived maximum load among all the computing nodes:

$$\max_{i \in [1, n]} \left(L_i + \sum_{j \in [1, q]} ET_{ij} \right)$$

where ET_{ij} is the execution time of task T_i on node C_j when T_i is assigned to node C_j , otherwise ET_{ij} is 0, and n is the number of tasks.

3.1.1 The simulation scenario

First many papers have been analyzed in order to choose an experimentation scenario detailed enough to be reconstituted and to suit the limited hardware and software resources. The goal is also to compare this work to other proposed solutions from the literature. The proposed solution was compared to:

- First-come-first-served algorithm (FCFS) [5]
- Dynamic Genetic load balancing Algorithm (DGA) [7]
- A hybrid load balancing strategy of sequential tasks for grid computing environments (HGA) [6]

The private Grid is composed of 5 nodes. The Grid resources are physically organized in a tree structure like in [26]. The simulation parameters (0) mentioned in [6] have been followed.

Table 1. Experimental parameters.

Parameters	Values
Number of computing nodes	5
Capacity of nodes	1
Number of tasks	250
Mean Inter-arrival Time	1s
Mean Computation length	5s

Several assumptions are made for the simulation:

- Tasks arrive and enter into the RMU, according to a Poisson process with rate λ .
- The expected computation lengths of tasks are assumed to follow an exponential distribution with a mean χ .
- The average capability C_i of node i , which is the relative ratio of its capability.
- Let ρ be the average system utilization factor for this simulation, which is the average task arrival rate divided by the average task processing rate [43]. According to this definition, the task computation length χ is adjusted in order to get the desired ρ .
- All the nodes used in the experiments, have the same processing capacity.
- The grid physical topology used in this experiment has a tree structure [26].

3.1.2 Evaluation of the system robustness

In this section, the system's performance is studied using the *makespan* metric and then the results are compared to the ones published in [6]. The *makespan* metric is widely used in the literature in order to measure the system robustness. In this experiment, the number of tasks is varied from 100 to 500 with an interval of 50. The mean computation length of the tasks χ is also varied to keep the average system utilization factor ρ at a value of 1.4.

Table .2 Measurement lists of makespan metric

Tasks	Makespan			
	DGA	FCFS	HGA	TunSys
100	100,90	94,10	90,60	85,09
150	137,60	132,80	129,20	124,04
200	196,60	184,90	181,00	183,01
250	230,10	230,40	222,50	235,00
300	275,70	269,10	265,90	261,03
350	326,70	315,40	312,00	312,13
400	361,90	356,40	352,40	352,00
450	422,10	413,10	407,30	414,09
500	466,00	459,20	456,40	462,07

As shown in 0, the *makespan* of tasks increases when the number of tasks grows since more tasks are seeking to be executed. The proposed method TunSys outperforms DGA and FCFS in all cases. In addition, it gives good results compared to HGA even though TunSys uses a simple Random scheduling policy and focuses on system load balancing while HGA integrates scheduling and load balancing optimization. According to these results, TunSys is able to accommodate and thus performs more robustly than DGA and FCFS and HGA in most cases.

3.1.3 Load-Balancing performance

In order to test the load balancing performance of these algorithms, two scenarios are used: homogeneous nodes and heterogeneous nodes with $\lambda=1.0$, average Poisson distribution=0.96, total tasks=100 and the utilization factor is varied between 0.8 to 1.5 by varying the tasks' length.

3.2 Performance under homogeneous nodes

All the nodes have the same processing capacity. The mean computation length χ is varied between 4 seconds and 7.5 seconds, and the average system utilization factor from 0.8 to 1.5. The tests are repeated ten times in order to get mean values of the load balancing.

The results (0 and **Error! Reference source not found.** and 0) show that, under homogeneous nodes scenario, the proposed method shows better stability than FCFS and HGA. In fact, even though the system utilization factor changes the load, distribution keeps stable (between 0.04 and 0.05) and varying in a limited interval. While for HGA, for example, the square deviation of node utilization varies between 0.01 and 0.126.

Furthermore, when the utilization factor is less than 1.1, TunSys outperforms clearly the other two solutions. However, when it becomes greater than 1.1, it is exceeded by FCFS and HGA. This can be explained by the fact that TunSys uses local thresholds to classify the state of a node as overloaded or not. So, the load balancing process is triggered only for nodes having their waiting queue length higher than the workload thresholds.

Table .3 The square deviation of node utilization under homogeneous nodes scenario

Average Utilization Factor	TunSys	FCFS	HGA
0.8	0.047	0.126	0.126
0.9	0.0502	0.072	0.072
1.0	0.044	0.054	0.052
1.1	0.049	0.046	0.042
1.2	0.0458	0.038	0.036
1.3	0.0498	0.03	0.028
1.4	0.046	0.034	0.018
1.5	0.047	0.034	0.01

Figure 5 The square deviation of nodes' utilization under homogeneous nodes scenario

Figure 6. Minimum, Maximum, Average and Standard deviation of the square deviation of nodes' utilization under homogeneous nodes scenario

3.2.1 Performance under heterogeneous nodes

In this case, the system performance is tested under a heterogeneous Grid system. Two nodes are randomly selected and fixed their relative capabilities which is doubled by the value of the others. The mean computation length χ is varied between 5.6 and 10.5 seconds and the average system utilization factor from 0.8 to 1.5. The simulations are repeated ten times in order to get mean values of the load balancing.

Once again, under heterogeneous nodes scenario (0), TunSys shows better performance and stability than FCFS and HGA. In fact, the load distribution varies in a limited interval between 0.074 and 0.091 even though the system utilization factor changes. It is only when it becomes greater than 1.3 that HGA outperforms TunSys. Again, this is due to the fact that the proposed solution focuses on the network in order to take the load balancing decisions not the utilization factor which makes it more efficient and stable to load variations.

Table .4 The square deviation of node utilization under homogeneous nodes scenario

Average Utilization Factor	TunSys	FCFS	HGA
0.8	0.091	0.3208	0.2541
0.9	0.081	0.3	0.1958
1.0	0.086	0.2791	0.1416
1.1	0.083	0.2708	0.1083
1.2	0.088	0.2666	0.1041
1.3	0.0747	0.2625	0.0666
1.4	0.087	0.2541	0.0541
1.5	0.0857	0.2539	0.0375

Figure .7 The square deviation of nodes' utilization under heterogeneous nodes scenario

Figure8 Minimum, Maximum, Average and Standard deviation of the square deviation of nodes' utilization under heterogeneous nodes scenario

Figure 9. Average percentage of executed tasks per resource considering resources with PE=2 vs. resources with PE=4.

0, presents the average percentage of executed tasks per resource. The goal is to study the load distribution in case some of the resources are more powerful than the rest. The results show that the load is well redistributed among the grid. The resources with PE=4 are executing more tasks (almost two times) than the resources equipped with PE=2 even though TunSysuses a blind scheduling policy.

3.2.2 Evaluation of the scalability

The experimentation scenario focuses on the system's scalability. The system's utilization factor is fixed at 0.8 while the number of resources is varied as follows: 10 - 20 - 30 - 40 - and 50 and the number of simulated tasks 100 - 1000 - 10000 with a mean computation length χ varying between 5.6 and 10.5 seconds. The remaining parameters are kept the same as in the first experimentation scenario. The resources are physically interconnected using the same topology as in [26]. However, they are arbitrary interconnected to the routers in order to reduce the effect of the physical topology. TunSys simulated under two cases: homogeneous resources and heterogeneous resources. In the case of heterogeneous resources, 50% of the nodes are randomly selected and fixed their relative capabilities (number of processing elements) to twice the value of the others. Finally, each experiment is repeated 10 times and the discussed results are the mean values so that the effects of the random parameters on the results can be reduced.

0 presents the average system makespan while varying the number of tasks and resources. As expected, the makespan value decreases by 38% up to 84% in the case of homogeneous resources and by 43% up to 84% in the case of heterogeneous resources (0). As shown in 0 the makespan value decreases almost linearly by 34% in average every time the number of resources increases by 10. Except in case of 100 tasks, the system does not scale well and the average speedup is about 11% which is absolutely normal for two reasons. *First of all*, the number of executed tasks is very limited, and *second*, the used blind scheduling policy which is affecting some of these tasks to distant resources neither consider the network transmission time nor forecast the load of the most close resources to the user submitting the tasks. As a conclusion, there is a linear and supra-linear scalability in case of 1000 and 10000 tasks.

Figure 10. Average makespan using 100, 1000, and 10000 tasks, 10-50 resources, and homogenous (—) vs. heterogeneous (—) resources.

Figure 11. System speedup in case of 100, 1000, and 10000 tasks running under 10 and 50 resources.

Figure 12. Average system speedup variation using 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 resources.

3.2.3 Load balancing performance

In order to study the load balancing performance of TunSys, which is the main goal, this section focuses on the percentage of executed tasks per resource. As expected, the system load is better distributed in case of homogeneous resources when considering the number of executed tasks per resource as shown in 0 and 0. In addition, every time the number of resources is increased by 10, the load balancing is improved especially when the system executes bigger number of tasks (0). This can lead to conclude that TunSys scales well. However how the system reacts in case of heterogeneous resources needs to be verified.

Figure 13. Mean square deviation of the percentage of executed tasks per resource in case of homogeneous resources.

Figure 14 Mean square deviation of the percentage of executed tasks per resource in case of heterogeneous resources.

Figure 15. Mean square deviation of the percentage of executed tasks per resource in case of homogenous (—) vs. heterogeneous (—) resources with 100, 1000, and 10000 tasks.

Figure 15. Average percentage of executed tasks per resource considering resources with PE=2 (—) vs. resources with PE=4 (—) .

The 0, presents the average percentage of executed tasks per resource. It compares the load distribution between most powerful resources (PE=4) and less powerful resources (PE=2). The results show that the load distribution is considering the resource performance represented by the

number of processing elements (PE). The most powerful resources are executing more tasks (more than the double especially in case of 10 nodes) except in case of 100 tasks which is due to the limited number of tasks and the blind scheduling policy TunSysuses.

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, a topology-aware load balancing method for grid computing systems is proposed. Based on a polyhedron logical model with a sphere-like structure, the proposed method ensures a local neighborhood load balancing strategy using a combination of a local and a global thresholds. The proposed load balancing method is implemented and evaluated within a simple blind scheduling strategy, since the load balancing problem is the aim of this work. GridSim simulator is used for experimental comparison between TunSys and FCFS, DGA, and HGA through the makespan and mean square deviation metrics.

The comparative evaluation of TunSys with FCFS, DGA and HGA shows encouraging results. In fact, the system performance (measured through makespan) shows that TunSys outperforms FCFS, DGA, and in most cases HGA. In addition, it shows an excellent system scalability that can reach linear and supra-linear levels in case of 1000 and 10000 tasks. Furthermore, TunSys shows good load balancing performance in terms of system stability by taking advantage of resource heterogeneity, and the scalability of its load balancing approach.

Currently, the goal is to optimize the load balancing solution by integrating a better scheduling policy. In addition, TunSys will be compared to other more recent works involving different logical models like star, tree, and peer-to-peer.

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